

Studies on Rutaceae—Part III. Reactions and Rearrangements of Prenyl and Prenyloxy Coumarins

J. BANERJI*, (Mrs.) A. CHATTERJEE, N. GHOSHAL, A. DAS, S. SARKAR,
S. BHATTACHARYA (in part) and J. N. SHOOLERY**

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

During our study on the reactions and rearrangements of prenyl and prenyloxy coumarins interesting reactions and rearrangements were observed. 7-Methoxy-8-(1',2'-epoxy-3'-methylbut-3'-enyl)coumarin (phebalosin) (II) on oxidation with osmium tetroxide afforded 7-methoxy-coumarin-8-yl-acetaldehyde (XXXII) while 7-methoxy-8-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methylbut 3'-enyl) coumarin (auraptanol) (III) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid underwent rearrangement to 7-methoxy-8-(3'-formyl-but-2'-enyl) coumarin (XXX). The epoxy-lactone system of 7-methoxy-coumarin-6-(3',4'-epoxy-3'-methyl)- γ -butyrolactone (micromelumun) (IV) opened up with boron tribromide to give 7-methoxy-coumarin-6-(3'-bromo-3'-methyl-4'-hydroxy)- γ -butyrolactone (XXXIII) while with 10% oxalic acid ring opening was accompanied by further degradation to give 6-formyl-7-methoxy coumarin (angelical) (XXXIV). Chromous chloride reduction of micromelumun (IV) afforded deoxymicromelumun (XXXVI) and oxidation with chromic acid/sulphuric acid degraded it to umbelliferone-methyl-ether-6-carboxylic acid (XXXVII). Dehydrogenation of dihydroseselin (VII) with DDQ resulted in an unusual product 3,6-dichloro-dihydroseselin (XXIV).

COUMARINS are widely distributed in the plant kingdom and are specially abundant in the families Umbelliferae and Rutaceae. A vast majority of such compounds carry an oxygen function at C-7 and also bear isopentenyl side chain(s). These therefore offer the best example of a class of compounds exhibiting greater number of biogenetic modifications of the simple isoprenoid unit than any other class of natural products known today. Various transformations with different reagents can be achieved involving these substituents resulting not only in the syntheses of coumarins already isolated from nature but also in the discovery of interesting reactions.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in a Kofler Block and are uncorrected. The spectra were recorded: uv (λ_{max} in nm and log in parenthesis) on a Varian Techtron 634 in 95% aldehyde-free ethanol; ir (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) on a Beckman IR-20 (KBr disc); pmr (chemical shift in δ , ppm) on Varian A-60D (60 MHz), CFT-20 (80 MHz) and XL-200 (200 MHz) spectrometers (CDCl_3 , d_6 -DMSO; internal standard, TMS). Column chromatography and tlc were carried out with silica gel (60-120 mesh, BDH and 60-100 mesh, Gouri Chemical Works, Calcutta). The analytical samples were dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 24 hr. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used for drying the organic extracts.

7-Methoxy-8-(3'-formylbut-2'-enyl) coumarin (XXX): Auraptanol (III) (100 mg) was treated with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (80 mg) in dry chloroform at 0° under nitrogen atmosphere for 3hr. Usual work up of the reaction mixture and chromatographic resolution on silica gel afforded XXX from benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) eluate, m. p. 121-22° (petrol-benzene), yield 22%; uv (EtOH): 207, 217 and 321 (4.41, 4.36 and 4.13); ir: 1725 (formyl carbonyl), 1680 (lactone carbonyl intermolecular hydrogen bonding) and 1570, 1500 (aromatic). (Found: C, 69.70; H, 5.48. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 69.76; H, 5.42%).

7-Methoxy-coumarin-6-(3'-bromo-3'-methyl-4'-hydroxy)- γ -butyrolactone (XXXIII): To a solution of micromelumun (IV) (100 mg) in anhydrous methylene chloride (10 ml) was added dropwise a solution of boron tribromide (0.4 ml) in methylene chloride (5.6 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at 0-5° for 1 hr. Usual work up of the reaction mixture and chromatographic resolution on silica gel afforded XXXIII from benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) eluate, m. p. 118-19° (benzene-ethyl acetate), yield 50%, uv (EtOH): 207, 223 and 323.5 (4.30, 4.21 and 4.13); ir: 3380 (hydroxy), 1790 (5 membered lactone ring), 1730 (α , β -unsaturated lactone), 1630 (>C=C<) and 1570, 1505 (aromatic). (Found: C, 48.80; H, 3.60. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_6\text{Br}$ requires C, 48.91; H, 3.53%).

*NMR Applications Laboratory, Varian Associates, Palo Alto, 611 Hansen Way, California 94303, U.S.A.

6-Formyl-7-methoxy coumarin (angelical) (XXXIV): Micromelum (IV) (500 mg) in methanol (60 ml) was heated at reflux temperature with 10% oxalic acid (100 ml) and the distillate led into a solution of 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine in aqueous hydrochloric acid. The water lost by evaporation was replaced at intervals from a dropping funnel. An orange 2,4-DNPH gradually separated from the 2,4-DNP solution and the distillation continued for 9-10 hr, until its formation became slow. The derivative was filtered, crystallized from rectified spirit as orange needles, m. p. 153-4°, yield 40%. It was shown to be identical with 2:4 DNPH of propionaldehyde (Found: N, 23.35. $C_9H_{10}N_4O_4$ requires N, 23.5%).

The non volatile part on extraction with chloroform, washing, drying and removal of solvent gave (XXXIV), m.p. 245-7° (ethyl acetate), yield 45%; (Found: C, 65.10; H, 3.99. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 64.71; H, 3.92%).

Deoxymicromelum (XXXVI): A solution of micromelum (IV) (500 mg) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was added dropwise through a separating funnel to a solution of chromous chloride prepared from $CrCl_2$ (1 g) through which CO_2 was bubbled continuously. After complete addition the whole system was allowed to stand at room temperature in CO_2 atmosphere for 48 hr. The mixture was then diluted and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer on washing, drying and removal of solvent afforded XXXVI, m.p. 204-5° (chloroform-methanol), yield 85%; uv (MeOH); 221, 245, 256 and 332 (4.22, 3.62, 3.55 and 4.20); ir: 1750 (γ -lactone carbonyl), 1730 (δ -lactone carbonyl) and 1620 ($C=C$). (Found: C, 66.99; H, 4.83. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.18; H, 4.41%).

Umbelliferone-methylether-6-carboxylic acid (XXXVII): To a solution of micromelum (IV) (190 mg) in 3% H_2SO_4 (38 ml) was added a solution of chromic acid (5.0 gm) in water (60 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 6 hr, cooled and extracted with ether (3 x 25 ml). The ether extract on washing, drying and removal of solvent afforded XXXVII, m. p. 256° (methanol), yield 56%; uv (EtOH): 207, 227 and 330 (4.16, 3.84 and 3.87); ir: 3540 br(-OH), 1740 (lactone carbonyl), 1670 (carboxyl), 1120 (ether linkage). (Found: C, 59.98; H, 3.71. $C_{11}H_8O_5$ requires C, 60.01; H, 3.63%).

7-Methoxy-coumarin-8-yl-acetaldehyde (XXXII): To a solution of phebalosin (II) (255 mg) in anhydrous benzene (10 ml) was added dropwise a solution of osmium tetroxide (250 mg) in benzene (10 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 hr. H_2S was then passed for osmate cleavage and osmium dioxide thus precipitated was removed by filtration. The filtrate on concentration and chromatographic reso-

lution on silica gel column afforded XXXII in benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) eluate, m. p. 156° (white shining flakes from benzene), yield 20%; uv (EtOH): 211, 248, 257 and 323 (4.45, 3.84, 3.88 and 4.48); ir: 1730 (formyl carbonyl and lactone carbonyl), 1610 ($C=C$) and 1570, 1500 (aromatic). (Found: C, 65.82; H, 4.62. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.05; H, 4.58%).

3,6-Dichlorodihydroseselin (XXIV): Dihydroseselin (VII) (100 mg) was dissolved in dry benzene (20 ml) and the solution was refluxed with DDQ (110 mg) for 50 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and dry HCl gas was passed through it for half an hr. The reaction was again refluxed for 1 hr. This process of refluxing and dry HCl gas passing was continued until the time of refluxing became 32 hr. The coloured reaction mixture was separated from white hydroquinol, washed with 2% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The benzene solution on concentration and chromatographic resolution on silica gel column afforded XXIV from petrol eluate, m.p. 163-5° (petrol), yield 54%; uv (EtOH): 231, 254, 265 and 343 (4.16, 3.65, 3.57 and 4.19); ir: 1720 (lactone carbonyl), 1605 ($C=C$) and 1580, 1460 (aromatic). (Found: C, 56.30; H, 4.10. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4Cl_2$ requires C, 56.37; H, 4.02%).

Results and Discussion

For our study we chose several naturally occurring coumarins bearing interesting and varied substitution patterns, viz., 7-methoxy-8-(3'-methylbut-2'-enyl) coumarin (osthol) (I), a major constituent of *Prangos pabularia* Lindl (Umbelliferae) and *Feronia limonia* Linn (Rutaceae), 7-methoxy-8-(1',2'-epoxy-3'-methylbut-3-enyl) coumarin (phebalosin) (II) and 7-methoxy-8-(2-hydroxy-3'-methylbut-3-enyl) coumarin (auraptanol) (III), both occurring abundantly in *Murraya exotica* Linn (Rutaceae), 7-methoxy coumarin-6-(3', 4'-epoxy-3'-methyl)- γ -butyrolactone (micromelum) (IV), a major constituent of *Micromelum pubescens* Blume (Rutaceae) and 5-(2',3'-epoxy-3'-methyl) *n*-butyloxy psoralen (oxypeucedanin) (V), another major component of *P. pabularia*. In the course of our studies^{1-4,7} on the chemical transformations of osthol (I) and its epoxide (VI) with various Lewis acids, unexpected reactions and rearrangements had been observed. This study was initiated with the object of elaborating easy routes to the pyrano- and furanocoumarins, dihydroseselin (VII), tetrahydroroselone (VIII), di-columbianetin (IX) and di-lomatatin (X), under mild conditions.

Friedel-Crafts reactions of I with toluene¹ and benzene² in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride resulted in arylation at C-4 with concomitant demethylation and disproportionation yield-

ding 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-isopentyl-4-tolyl (XII) and 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-isopentyl-4-phenyl (XI) coumarins in addition to 7-methoxy-8-isopentyl-coumarin (XIII). Under these reaction conditions it is apparent that the aryl radical attacks the benzylic site followed by disproportionation of the C₈-isopentenyl side chain and demethylation. However, in a later study⁸ with anisole, arylation occurred at C-3' giving rise to 7-methoxy-8-(3'-anisyl) isopentyl (XIV) and 7-methoxy-8-(3'-*p*-hydroxyphenyl) isopentyl (XV) coumarins in addition to XIII. The addition of the anisole moiety to the tertiary carbon at C-3' is possibly due to its predominant anionic character, the anion being stabilised through its aluminium chloride complex.

XXV

Boron trifluoride catalysed isomerisation, transformation and condensation reactions are well known. During our study of the rearrangements of peroxy coumarins with this reagent we were able to develop from osthol (I), via its epoxide (VI), an efficient synthesis^{1,4} of 7-methoxy-8-(2'-formyl-2'-methyl-propyl) coumarin (XVI), a major lactonic constituent of *Citrus decumana* Linn (Rutaceae) in

addition to the ketone, isoauraptene (XVII). The formation of the unusual product XVI can be rationalized to occur via a pinacol-pinacolone type of rearrangement involving the migration of the aryl part of the molecule to the incipient carbonium ion at C-3'. Isoauraptene (XVII) is produced by the migration of the hydride ion at C-2' to C-3'. Boron trifluoride has also been successfully used for the syntheses of two naturally occurring C-5 prenylated furocoumarins of *P. pabularia*, 5-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methylene-*n*-butyloxy)-psoralen (pabulenol)⁵ (XVIII) and 5-(2'-keto-3'-methyl-*n*-butyloxy)-psoralen (isoxypeucedanin) (XIX) through the rearrangement⁶ of the epoxide, oxypeucedanin (V). With boron trifluoride phebalosin (II) rearranged³ smoothly to 7-methoxy-8-(1'-formyl-2'-methyl-prop-1'-enyl)-coumarin (XX). The formation of this product possibly occurred via a pinacol-pinacolone type of rearrangement with migration of the aryl part of the molecule to C-2'. Investigation⁷ of the reaction of osthol (I) with boron trifluoride resulted in the formation of its Δ^{3'}-isomer (XXI). This contra-thermodynamic isomerisation appears to be interesting as the Δ^{2'}-bond of osthol (I) migrates to a terminal position rather than to a conjugated site (Δ^{1'}).

Synthesis of Pabulenol and Isoxypeucedanin

The use of boron tribromide as an effective demethylating agent is well known⁸⁻¹². However, with osthol (I) and its epoxide (VI) different products were obtained depending on the molar concentration of the reagent¹. With one mole equivalent of the reagent I yielded 7-methoxy-8-(3'-hydroxy-3'-methyl butyl) coumarin (XXII) while excess of the reagent brought about demethylation and cyclisation to dihydroseselin (VII). This on dehydrogenation would lead to seselin (XXIII). In a programme on the synthesis of angular pyrano- and furanocoumarins by functionalisation of the double bond in the pyran ring of XXIII we attempted a dehydrogenation reaction of VII, dissolved in dry benzene, with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzoquinone under refluxing conditions. Instead of the expected compound XXIII we obtained XXIV. In the formation of compound XXIV apparently normal substitution took place at C₆ along with addition of chlorine at Δ^{8,4} followed by a dehydrohalogenation step.

Osthol epoxide (VI) with excess of boron tribromide was smoothly transformed¹ to dihydro-oro-selone (XXV). With one mole equivalent of the reagent the major product was 7-methoxy-8-(2'-3'-dihydroxy-3'-methyl butyl)-coumarin (XXVI).

While using this reagent we had anticipated the demethylation of phebalosin (II) and subsequent cyclisation to oroselone (XXVII). However, II underwent an interesting rearrangement⁸ to 2'-bromoselin (XXVIII) which on reduction with zinc and acetic acid afforded seselin (XXIII).

In a recent study directed towards the synthesis of casegraval¹³ (XXIX) a naturally occurring coumarin of *Casearia graveolens* Dalz (Samy-daceae) we contemplated the use of two starting materials, auraptenol (III) and phebalosin (II). The former on epoxidation followed by a dehydration step with subsequent ring opening of the oxirane function would directly lead to the coumarin XXIX. However, auraptenol (III) on treatment with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in chloroform at 0° under a nitrogen cover underwent rearrangement to 7-methoxy-8-(3'-formyl-but-2'-enyl) coumarin (XXX). This product must have been formed via the epoxide with subsequent removal of proton from C-4' and elimination of water. In the second approach we had intended to generate the vicinal glycol at C-3' and C-4' (XXXI) by treating II with osmium tetroxide followed by removal of the oxirane ring with triphenylphosphine to generate the olefinic linkage. However, oxidation with osmium tetroxide in dry benzene containing catalytic amount of pyridine resulted in the formation of 7-methoxy-coumarin-8-yl-acetaldehyde (XXXII). The latter is probably formed via the vicinal glycol (XXXI) followed by opening of the oxirane function and rupture of the C-2'-C-3' bond.

Rearrangement of auraptenol III

The presence of an epoxy-lactone system in the 5-carbon unit attached at C-6 in micromelumun (IV) offered an interesting system for study. This was resistant to boron trifluoride. The epoxy ring could, however be easily opened with boron tribromide in dry methylene chloride at 0-5° yielding 7-methoxy-coumarin-6-(3-bromo-3'-methyl-4'-hydroxy)- γ -butyrolactone (XXXIII). However on refluxing with 10% oxalic acid in methanol the epoxy ring opened up accompanied by further degradation to give

Reactions and rearrangement of phebalosin II

6-formyl-6-methoxy-coumarin (angelical) (XXXIV) in addition to propionaldehyde (XXXV) which was characterised as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The generation of a double bond with chromous chloride reduction is a characteristic reaction of an epoxy-lactone. Micromelumun (IV) on treatment with chromous chloride in glacial acetic acid at 25° yielded 3',4'-deoxymicromelumun (XXXVI). On oxidation with chromic acid-sulphuric acid in water under reflux, it underwent degradation to umbelliferone-methyl ether-6-carboxylic acid (XXXVII). The identity of both the products, XXXIV and XXXVII, was established by comparison with authentic samples.

Reactions of micromelumun

The 80 MHz ^1H nmr spectrum in CDCl_3 of 3,6-dichlorodihydroseleselin (XXIV), $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$ (M^+ 298, 300 and 302) was highly significant. The coumarin C-4 proton resonated at 7.62 (1H, s) and the aromatic C-5 at 7.21 (1H, s). The two methyls at C-2' of the pyran ring showed the characteristic six proton singlet at 1.36. The C-3' and C-4' methylenes appeared as triplets at 1.82 and 2.86 respectively (2H each, $J_1=J_2=7.0$ Hz). 7-Methoxy-8-(3'-formyl-but-2'-enyl) coumarin (XXX), $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 258) showed in its 80 MHz ^1H nmr spectrum in CDCl_3 the characteristic coumarin doublets at 6.25 (C-3) and 7.66 (C-4) (1H, each $J=9.5$ Hz) and two aromatic *ortho*-protons at 7.37 (C-5) and 6.86 (C-6) (1H, d each $J=8.0$ Hz). The vinyl methyl resonated as a singlet at 1.95 (3H), the benzylic methylene at C-1' as a doublet at 3.90 (2H, $J=6.5$ Hz) and the methoxy group (C-7) as a singlet at 3.95 (3H). The formyl proton exhibited a singlet at 9.36. The downfield one proton signal at 6.5 (t, $J_1=J_2=6.5$ Hz) was justifiably attributed to the vinyl methine at C-2' which is in conjugation with the formyl group.

7-Methoxy-coumarin-8-yl - acetaldehyde (XXXII) $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 218) showed in its 80 MHz ^1H nmr spectrum in CDCl_3 the characteristic coumarin doublets at 6.21 (C-3) and 7.63 (C-4) (1H each, $J=9.0$ Hz) and two aromatic *ortho* protons at 7.40 (C-5) and 6.85 (C-6) (1H, d each, $J=8.0$ Hz). The benzylic methylene (C-1') appeared at 3.95 (2H, s) and the methoxy group at 3.88 (3H, s). The formyl proton resonated as a broad singlet at 9.72.

The 200 MHz ^1H nmr spectrum in CDCl_3 of 7-methoxy - coumarin-6 - (3' bromo - 3' - methyl-4' hydroxy)- γ -butyrolactone (XXXIII), $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_6\text{Br}$ (M^+ 368 and 370) showed the characteristic coumarin doublets at 6.33 (C-3) and 7.71 (C-4) (1H each, $J=10.0$ Hz). The C-8 and C-5 aromatic protons resonated as 1H singlets each at 6.89 and 7.53 (with finer splitting, $J=1.0$ Hz), the C-3' methyl and C-7 methoxyl at 2.03 and 4.02 (3H s each) respectively.

The benzylic methine (C-5') appeared as a doublet with finer splitting at 5.53 ($J_1=4.0$, $J_2=1.0$ Hz) while the doublet at 4.86 ($J=4.0$ Hz) was attributed to C-4' proton. This fine splitting is possibly due to coupling with the aromatic proton at C-5. The singlet at 3.63 (disappearing on deuteration) is due to the hydroxyl at C-4'.

Deoxymicromelumun (XXXVI), $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ (M^+ 272) showed in its 60 MHz ^1H nmr spectrum in d_6 -DMSO the characteristic coumarin doublets at 6.14 (C-3) and 7.75 (C-4) (1H each, $J=9.0$ Hz) and two one proton singlets at 6.90 (C-8) and 7.32 (C-5) indicating their *para*-disposition. In the aromatic region the one proton doublets each at 6.09 ($J=4.0$ Hz) and 7.38 ($J=4.0$ Hz) were attributed to the C-5' and C-4' protons respectively. The C-3' methyl and C-7 methoxyl group resonated as singlets (3H each) at 1.85 and 3.90 respectively.

The structures of compounds (XXIV), (XXX), (XXXII) and (XXXIII) were further confirmed from their ^{13}C nmr data (Table 1).

TABLE—1 CARBON-13 NMR SIGNALS (δ) of 3,6-DICHLORODIHYDROSELESIN (XXIV), 7-METHOXY-8-(3'-FORMYL-BUT-2'-ENYL)-COUMARIN (XXX), 7-METHOXY-COUMARIN-8-YL ACETALDEHYDE (XXXII) AND 7-METHOXY-COUMARIN-6-3'-BROMO-3'-METHYL-4'-HYDROXY- γ -BUTYROLACTONE (XXXIII) IN CDCl_3 .

	XXIV	XXX	XXXII	XXXIII
C-2	154.20	160.80	160.95	160.0
C-3	118.40	113.28	113.31	114.0
C-4	138.70	143.62	143.27	143.0
C-4a	111.10	113.05	113.6	112.10
C-5	125.0	127.33	127.90	125.80
C-6	119.30	107.34	107.30	122.0
C-7	152.40	160.24	158.95	159.0
C-8	110.50	114.20	117.0	99.20
C-8a	149.70	152.94	153.50	155.80
C-7OCH ₃		56.15	56.14	56.0
C-1'		22.78	37.72	
C-2'	76.5	150.75	197.45	173.10
C-3'	31.0	139.75		54.0
C-4'	16.8	9.25		81.0
C-5'				81.80
C-2' $\begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases}$	26.30			
C-3'-CH ₃		195.50		21.6
C-3'-CHO				

Acknowledgements

Sincere thanks are accorded to Dr. A. Patra, Dept. of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University for critical discussion and suggestions and to Sri A. K. Acharya Sri P. Ghosh, Sri J. Ghosh and Sri P. Pal of the Organic Instrumentation Laboratory, Dept. of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University, for spectral measurements and to U.G.C. (India) and C. C. R. A. S. (India), for financial assistance.

References

- J. BANERJI, R. N. REJ. (MRS.) A. CHATTERJEE and A. BANERJI, *Indian J. Chem.* 1979, 17B, 113.
- J. BANERJI (NE'E CHATTERJEE), S. C. BASA and (MRS.) A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Chem. Soc., Section C*, 1971, 3992.
- J. BANERJI, N. BHADURI, R. N. REJ, J. N. SHOOLERY, S. MUKHERJEE and S. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, 19B, 341.
- A. CHATTERJEE, R. N. REJ, A. BANERJI and J. BANERJI, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1976, 410.
- S. C. BASA, J. CHATTERJEE and (MRS.) A. CHATTERJEE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 1977.
- A. CHATTERJEE, J. BANERJI and S. C. BASA, *Tetrahedron*, 1972, 28, 5175.
- J. BANERJI and R. N. REJ, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1974, 529.
- J. F. W. MCOMIE, M. L. WATTS and D. E. WEST, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, 24, 2289.
- I. VLATTAS, I. T. HARRISON, L. TOKES, J. H. FRIED and A. D. CROSS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 23, 4176.
- F. L. BENTON and T. R. DILLION, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1128.
- J. F. W. MCOMIE and M. L. WATTS, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1963, 1658.
- W. SEHATER and B. FRANCK, *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, 99, 160.
- S. K. TALAPATRA, S. GOSWAMI, N. C. GANGULY and B. TALAPATRA, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1980, 154.